

CAPSID: A Private Session ID System for Small UAVs

Yueshen Li*
yueshen7@illinois.edu
University of Illinois
Urbana, Illinois, USA

Jianli Jin*
jianlij2@illinois.edu
University of Illinois
Urbana, Illinois, USA

Kirill Levchenko
klevchen@illinois.edu
University of Illinois
Urbana, Illinois, USA

ABSTRACT

The US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) has recently mandated that small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) be equipped with a transmitter that broadcasts the UAV’s serial number, location, and altitude. The inclusion of a unique identifier in the form of a UAV serial number has stoked fears that the identifier will be used to track UAV operators and has even led some UAV operators to file a lawsuit against the FAA.

In this paper, we propose CAPSID, an implementation of the FAA session ID concept that provides message authentication—something current Remote ID implementations lack—and strong operator anonymity. The FAA (or its equivalent in other jurisdictions) retains the ability to de-anonymize operators, but only in circumstances prescribed by law. To make this possible, CAPSID introduces a partially trusted third party, the Custodian, that serves as the bridge between anonymous identifiers and true operator identity. The Custodian ensures that the legal requirements for de-anonymization are met, preventing unnecessary mass collection of personally identifying information by a government agency.

We formally verify the message authentication property of CAPSID using a cryptographic protocol checker and provide a formal proof of identifier non-linkability, even in the presence of corrupt (but non-colluding) authorities.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growth in the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), commonly known as drones, has ushered in a new era of possibilities and challenges. Drones have found applications ranging from aerial photography to parcel delivery, transforming industries and enhancing convenience. However, their widespread adoption has also brought about regulatory complexities.

Highly publicized incidents of UAVs flying over airports and areas of national security concern, such as the White House and Disneyland, have led the US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) to require all small UAVs to be equipped with a transmitter that broadcasts UAV location and identification information. The system, called Remote ID, raises privacy concerns because it allows anyone to track UAVs, and, therefore, their operators, across flights.

The FAA argued that Remote ID would aid situation awareness, increasing safety throughout, and would enable enforcement actions against operators found to be in violation of flight rules. Our work is based on the observation that only the latter requires linking the UAV to its operator, while situation awareness requires only that UAVs use a consistent identifier during flight.

To address privacy concerns, the FAA has proposed—but not yet implemented—using ephemeral session IDs instead of serial numbers to identify UAVs in Remote ID broadcasts. Unfortunately,

even in its session ID proposal, the FAA has insisted on retaining the ability to link all session IDs to operators at all times. We believe this to be unnecessary.

In this work, we propose CAPSID, a protocol for small UAV identification that can serve as an implementation of the session ID concept. CAPSID meets the essential Remote ID requirements without revealing every UAV operator’s identity to anyone, including the FAA. To satisfy the FAA’s legitimate need to enforce laws and regulations, CAPSID provides an *unsealing* mechanism to de-anonymize otherwise anonymous UAV identifiers when the legal requirements for doing so are met. To do so, we introduce a partially-trusted third party we call the Custodian. The Custodian maintains information linking anonymous UAV identifiers used in Remote ID broadcasts to another set of anonymous identifiers that can be linked to individual operators only by the FAA. The Custodian can reveal the link between the two kinds of identifiers to the FAA when it (or another government agency) has met the legal requirements for unsealing. CAPSID is policy-agnostic, relying on the Custodian to enforce a jurisdiction’s privacy laws. In addition to its gatekeeper role, the Custodian can also provide process transparency by reporting statistics on unsealing requests, allowing public watchdogs to monitor the system for abuses. It can also delete linking information after a certain period, if mandated by law.

CAPSID has three security properties that we believe are essential for a private session ID system:

Off-line verifiable. All flight information broadcasts are signed, allowing any receiver to verify that the broadcast originated from a UAV registered with the licensing authority (FAA in the United States). Authentication does not require an Internet connection nor two-way communication with the UAV.

Traceable. Every verified broadcast can be traced to an operator. Unsealing an operator’s identity requires cooperation between the FAA and the Custodian; neither can unseal an identity unilaterally. Moreover, CAPSID protects against impersonation, even by a corrupt Custodian.

Long-term unlinkable. A UAV uses a consistent identifier during a flight, providing short-term linkability that allows a receiver to monitor the UAV’s path. However, a UAV’s long-term identifiers change daily, preventing anyone from linking Remote ID broadcasts from one day to another, ensuring anonymity for operators. This non-linkability property holds even if the licensing authority or Custodian is corrupt.

CAPSID uses standard cryptographic tools to achieve this: digital signatures, tweakable symmetric block ciphers, an append-only public ledger, and a commitment scheme.

*Both authors contributed equally to this work.

In summary, we make the following contributions:

- ❖ We describe CAPSID, a protocol for anonymous UAV identification. CAPSID protects operator privacy, while providing flight information authentication and identity unsealing when required by law.
- ❖ We formally verify the broadcast verification and tracing mechanism of CAPSID using ProVerif, a cryptographic protocol verifier.
- ❖ We prove the non-linkability property of CAPSID, even against a corrupt Authority or Custodian.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the necessary background. Section 3 describes our threat model and provides an overview of our protocol. Section 4 describes CAPSID in detail. Section 5 provides a security analysis of CAPSID. Section 6 discusses issues raised by our work. Section 7 describes related work. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 BACKGROUND

This section begins by describing current US Remote ID regulations and note the privacy concerns they raise. We use the stated motivation for Remote ID to formulate the intended requirements for Remote ID, augmented with additional requirements to protect UAV operator privacy.

2.1 Current Remote ID Regulations

On January 15, 2021, the US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), which is the government body charged with regulating civil aviation in the United States, established a requirement that all small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) must broadcast real-time identification and position information, unless they are being flown recreationally and weigh less than 250 grams (14 CFR 89.305¹). The information in the broadcast must include:

- (a) The identity of the unmanned aircraft, consisting of:
 - (1) A serial number assigned to the unmanned aircraft by the person responsible for the production of the standard remote identification unmanned aircraft; or
 - (2) A session ID.
- (b) The latitude and longitude of the control station.
- (c) The geometric altitude of the control station.
- (d) The latitude and longitude of the unmanned aircraft.
- (e) The geometric altitude of the unmanned aircraft.
- (f) The velocity of the unmanned aircraft.
- (g) The current time (UTC).
- (h) An indication of the emergency status of the UAV.

The FAA did not specify a particular method for broadcasting the information, requiring only that it be “a non-proprietary broadcast specification and using radio frequency spectrum compatible with personal wireless devices ...” (14 CFR 89.320). In practice, the most popular means of compliance is by implementing the ASTM F3411 standard [3], which uses WiFi Aware or Bluetooth to broadcast the message elements above.

Public response. The FAA received 53,000 comments during the public comment period for the proposed rule [19]. Among the concerns raised by the public were the cost of compliance [19, p. 4480] and privacy [19, p. 4432]. Our work proposes a new protocol that increases the privacy protections and addresses the privacy concerns raised by the public.

RaceDayQuads v. FAA. In August 2021, seven months after the final rule was issued, but before the mandated compliance date of September 16, 2023, RaceDayQuads, an online UAV store, filed a case in US Federal Court challenging the FAA rule as unconstitutional [32, 43]. Backed by a crowd-funding campaign to pay its legal costs, RaceDayQuads argued that the Remote ID requirement infringes upon reasonable expectations of privacy, writing:

FAA has stated repeatedly in the final rule and elsewhere that Remote ID is like a digital license plate in the sky. It is not. The registration number on the drone is analogous to a license plate while Remote ID is a GPS tracking device that broadcasts not just a registration number but GPS coordinates of the drone and controller that can be monitored and logged by FAA, law enforcement and potentially others. The sheer overbreadth of this rule-making destroys any analogy to a license plate on the road. The final rule is analogous to requiring all vehicles, including go-peds and lawn mowers on private property, to pay for and install GPS tracking beacons for law enforcement to monitor and archive. [34, pp. 19–20]

Although the suit ultimately failed at the DC Appeals Court, it has gained widespread social attention. At the heart of this legal battle was the conviction that a hobbyist UAV is inextricably linked to an individual, and that enabling the government to collect such information amounts to mass surveillance.

Identifiers. UAV operators must register the serial numbers appearing in the broadcast message (element (a)(1) above) with the FAA. This allows the FAA to link a UAV’s Remote ID broadcast to a specific operator. However, because the serial number is a persistent identifier, even a receiver without access to drone registration information can logically link multiple flights of the same UAV. The serial number acts as a pseudonym which, once linked to an individual by some other means, allows re-identification of the same individual.²

Session ID. An alternative to using a UAV serial number is the session identifier. The name suggests that this is an ephemeral identifier allowing the same drone to be traced during a flight but not across flights. Unfortunately, the session ID concept was proposed in the context of an Internet-based mode of transmitting the Remote ID information that was abandoned for the final rule. The FAA has stated that it plans to allow session IDs to be used in broadcast Remote ID as well; however, as of this writing, there is no way to use session IDs. It should be noted that the session ID mechanism, when it is implemented, would only hide persistent

¹References of the form (14 CFR 89.305) are to the United States *Code of Federal Regulations*.

²Strictly speaking, a UAV *operator* is the person or legal entity legally responsible for the UAV, and may be distinct from the UAV *pilot*, the person controlling the UAV during flight. In recreational use, however, the operator and pilot are the same individual.

UAV identifiers from the public. The FAA stated that “law enforcement and the FAA will be able to correlate each session ID to a specific unmanned aircraft serial number, but that this ability will not be publicly available.” [19, p. 4417] Furthermore, “the FAA does not agree, however, that session ID be the default option, and instead finds that both session ID and the serial number are equally acceptable” [19, p. 4418].

Our work may be viewed as a proposal for implementing the session ID concept in a way that hides persistent identifiers not only from the public but *also* from the government. Our proposal allows authorized users to de-anonymize session IDs when necessary, in a manner similar to identity escrow. Our mechanism provides the option for public accountability and enforcement of de-anonymization policy by relying on a trusted third party.

2.2 Outside the United States

UAV registration requirements have recently been introduced outside the United States, as well, notably in the European Union and Japan. While the motivation for our work is the US FAA’s Remote ID system, as described below, other Remote ID systems are largely the same.

2.2.1 European Union. UAV registration and operation requirements in the European Union are similar to those of the United States. Specifically, European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA)—the agency that oversees civil aviation in Europe—requires operators to register with their country’s aviation authority, unless their drone weights less than 250 grams and either has neither camera nor sensor to capture personal data, or has been classified as a toy.

UAVs are categorized into classes based on primarily on weight and capability. Category C0 consist of drones weighing less than 250 grams; categories C1 through C3 cover UAVs of increasing weight and capabilities; category C4 is used for intended aircraft. Categories are restricted in how close to people they can operate: categories C2 and above may not fly over people, categories C3 and above may maintain a safe distance from people (at least 50 meters, as suggested by the FAA).

Remote ID information elements. UAV categories C1 through C3 are required to broadcast Remote ID information starting January 1, 2024, consisting of operator registration number, UAV serial number, UAV position and course, remote pilot location, and UAV emergency status [17]. In contrast to the FAA’s Remote ID, operators in the EU do not register UAVs with EASA or their national aviation authority; instead, the broadcast contains the operator registration number. EASA has no provisions for an ephemeral session ID instead of the operator registration number and UAV serial number.

2.2.2 Japan. Starting June 20, 2022, all UAVs weighing 100 grams or more must broadcast Remote ID information in accordance with the ASTM F3411 standard [3] at least once per second [24]. The Remote ID broadcast must contain: UAV registration ID, UAV serial number, current UAV location, current UAV speed, time, and a message authentication code computed over the message.

The message authentication code is generated using AES-128 in CCM mode (the ciphertext itself is discarded). The UAV secret key for the above is provided to the UAV by the operator along with the UAV registration number and registration validity period,

who obtains it from the Japan Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism (MLIT). MLIT digitally signs the registration information block provided to the operator. The UAV must verify the signature on this information block before accepting the registration information. The MLIT public key used to verify the signature is provided to the manufacturer of the UAV, who includes it in the UAV firmware.

2.3 Problems with Remote ID

Before proceeding to describe our proposal, it is worth articulating the problem with the current Remote ID systems (with and without session IDs).

Unverifiable by unprivileged receivers. An unprivileged receiver that does not have access to FAA databases has no way to determine if a UAV is properly registered. A UAV can broadcast a fictitious UAV serial number or session ID. The ability of any receiver to determine whether a UAV has been properly registered would make it easier to identify non-compliance, as private citizens can report unregistered UAV operations.

A malicious operator can also make fictitious broadcasts, making it appear that a swarm of UAVs are in an area, which may cause mass mayhem. ADS-B, a system used for manned aircraft, is well-known to suffer the same shortcoming.

Unauthenticated. The FAA’s current Remote ID system, nor the proposed session ID extension, do anything to prevent a malicious operator from impersonating another. Likewise, with the EASA Remote ID system.³ Japan’s Remote ID system uses a feature of the ASTM F3411 standard [3] to authenticate broadcasts. Provided that the attacker does not intercept the registration information provided by MLIT to an operator, Japan’s implementation provides protection from impersonation.

Mass surveillance. As noted above, using the UAV serial number to identify a UAV in flight allows anyone to track the UAV over its lifetime, which ultimately allows anyone track the location and activity of UAV operators. In the case of business use, this may reveal information that would otherwise be considered proprietary. The ability to collect UAV location information at scale challenges the counterargument that this information is already public, as anyone can observe a UAV and its operator.

The session ID proposal, as it currently stands, is an improvement. However, it still allows the government and (potentially companies contracted by the government) to track UAVs and their operators. Our proposal is based on the observation that it is not necessary for anyone, including the FAA, to know which UAV is operating in a given area, only to know that it is there. Only in extreme circumstances, such as when a UAV breaks a rule, does the FAA need to be able to identify the UAV and its operator.

Given the similarity of Remote ID systems in the EU and Japan to the Remote ID system in the US, the rest of the paper takes the

³In the EASA Remote ID system, operator identifiers include a check character that is generated by computing a checksum over the registration number proper and a randomly-generated three-character secret code. When providing the operator registration number to the UAV, the operator includes the check character and three-character secret code. The UAV verifies the checksum and discards the secret code. Although easily circumvented, this mechanism appears intended to prevent simply providing another operator’s number to the UAV.

US system as a concrete target. We believe that our proposal would meet the requirements of other jurisdictions equally well.

3 CAPSID PRELIMINARIES

This section introduces several important concepts and provides an overview of the Custodian-Assisted Private Session ID (CAPSID) protocol. Section 4 explains the operation in detail.

3.1 Participants

A CAPSID system has the following participants:

- **Authority.** The Authority is responsible for licensing UAV operators and registering UAVs for operation in a given jurisdiction. In the United States, the Authority is the FAA.
- **Operator.** An operator is the party legally responsible for a UAV’s operation. Operators must be licensed by the Authority and must register any UAV they operate with the Authority.
- **UAV (transmitter).** An unmanned aerial vehicle equipped with a transmitter that is responsible for broadcasting the real-time identification and position information—*flight information* for short—containing elements (a) through (h) listed in Section 2.1. We assume that the transmitter has a reliable way to obtain this information from other UAV systems and consider attacks on UAV hardware to be out of scope. The transmitter may either be integrated or a discrete after-market component; however, as far as the protocol is concerned, the UAV and its transmitter are synonymous.
- **Receiver.** The receiver is a device capable of receiving and decoding broadcast messages from the UAV. The receiver does not require any two-way communication to operate.
- **Custodian.** The Custodian is a partially-trusted third party introduced by CAPSID to mediate the process of unsealing operator identities. The Authority trusts the Custodian to adhere to the CAPSID protocol and to unseal operator identities only after the Authority has met the legal prerequisites. Similarly, operators trust the Custodian to unseal identities solely when these legal conditions are fulfilled. We discuss potential candidates for this role in practice in Section 6.1.

CAPSID does not assume that the UAV (or discrete transmitter module) is trusted. Remote ID regulations require that, “The unmanned aircraft must be designed and produced in a way that reduces the ability of a person to tamper with the remote identification functionality” (14 CFR 89.310). In practice, we believe that it will be difficult to prevent someone from disabling the Remote ID transmitter. Once disabled, a malicious operator can install their own Remote ID transmitter. Therefore, CAPSID goes so far as to assume that the operator has full control of the transmitter, and relies on other protocol mechanisms—digital signatures and certificates—to allow any receiver to ensure compliance. An alternative may be to rely on some form of trusted hardware. We discuss this possibility briefly in Section 6.3.

Each operator has a unique **operator identifier (OID)** assigned to her⁴ by the Authority. Each UAV has a **UAV identifier (UID)** that

need not be unique across operators. The UID may be a manufacturer serial number, some form of universally unique identifier [26], an operator-specific counter incremented by the Authority for each UAV registered by the operator, or an identifier chosen by the operator. The combination of a OID and UID must refer to a single UAV as registered with the Authority. A UAV may have multiple UIDs, but it should use the same UID during the entire flight. The UID should be viewed as a tag or nickname used to refer to the UAV. From an enforcement point of view, what is important is to be able to identify the operator over a given UAV flight, should it become necessary to do so.

We explicitly do *not* assume the existence of a PKI that allows operators to prove their identity. Instead, we assume some out-of-band means for operators to establish an identity with the Authority and obtain unique OIDs. Assuming the existence of a PKI would allow us to protect against certain impersonation attacks by a powerful corrupt Authority. Unfortunately, this would also doom our proposal on arrival as impractical. Most countries do not have a universal individual PKI, nor have plans to create one. We assume, therefore, that the Authority is the sole bridge between operators’ identities in CAPSID and their real-life identities.

3.2 Threat Model

We consider five possible attackers: a miscreant operator, an honest but curious Authority, and honest but curious Custodian, a corrupt Authority, and a corrupt Custodian.

Miscreant operator. The miscreant operator participates in a CAPSID system as a properly licensed operator. She can register one or more real or fictitious UAVs with the Authority. She can operate any number of receivers and can make arbitrary flight information broadcasts.

Honest but curious Authority. An honest but curious Authority faithfully executes the CAPSID protocol, but tries to learn as much information as possible about operator activity. It does not collude with any other participant, does not impersonate real operators, and does not attempt to register fictitious UAVs or operators. It can see all UAV broadcasts, but cannot see the communication between operators and the Custodian.

Honest but curious Custodian. An honest but curious Custodian faithfully executes the CAPSID protocol, but tries to learn as much information as possible about operator activity. It does not collude with any other participant, does not impersonate real operators, and does not attempt to register fictitious UAVs or operators. It can see all UAV broadcasts, but cannot see the communication between operators and the Authority.

Corrupt Authority. The corrupt Authority does not need to follow the CAPSID protocol. It can create fictitious operators and UAVs, make arbitrary broadcasts, and interact with the Custodian using its fictitious identities. It does *not* collude with the Custodian, which is assumed to be operating honestly in this threat model. It can see all UAV broadcasts, but *cannot* see the communication between operators and the Custodian. Since all identities in the system are managed by the Authority—there is no independent PKI—we do not consider attacks where the corrupt Authority attempts to implicate an innocent operator in wrongdoing.

⁴We use the pronouns *she* and *her* to refer to the operator. We use the pronouns *it* and *its* to refer to the Authority, Custodian, UAV, and receiver.

Corrupt Custodian. The corrupt Custodian does not need to follow the CAPSID protocol. It can create fictitious operators and UAVs, make arbitrary broadcasts, and interact with the Authority using its fictitious identities. It can see all UAV broadcasts, but *cannot* see the communication between operators and the Authority.

The corrupt Authority and corrupt Custodian are very powerful attackers. Since they play a critical role in the system, we do not consider denial of service by either of them.

Additional assumptions. We assume that the attacker has access to current technology and computational resources, but not the ability to circumvent current cryptographic algorithms believed to be secure.

We assume that all participants have a secure and reliable channel to the Authority, for example, using TLS. We assume that the Authority provides a mechanism for licensed operators to authenticate to the Authority over the reliable communication channel, for example using credentials obtained at time of registration. We assume that, prior to operation, the operator has physical possession of the UAV and has a secure channel for communicating with the UAV (e.g. a physical USB connection). The channel provides confidentiality and mutual authentication (UAV knows it is talking to its operator, and the operator knows that she is talking to the UAV). We consider attacks against UAV hardware and the channel between operator and UAV to be out of scope. We assume that all participants have a means to determine the correct time to within a second, as might be necessary for checking certificate expiration.

3.3 Operational Epochs

One of the central concepts in CAPSID is that of an *operational epoch*. In CAPSID, an operational epoch consists of all flights that start on the same UTC day, where a UTC day is the 24-hour period starting on midnight UTC. CAPSID guarantees that an operators' flights cannot be linked across operational epochs by assigning a different session ID to the operator in a given epoch. We call this property long-term non-linkability. Within an operational epoch, a UAV is consistently identified by the same session ID. A UAV flights that spans across midnight UTC continues to operate in the previous day's epoch—it does not change its session ID mid-flight.

The CAPSID session ID takes the form of an encrypted UID. The encryption is deterministic within the same operational epoch, providing a consistent identifier.

3.4 Security Properties

CAPSID is designed to overcome the shortcomings of the Remote ID protocol, as enumerated in Section 2.3. Specifically, CAPSID provides the following three properties, defined informally below. (Section 5 defines these more formally.)

- **Verifiable.** An unprivileged receiver must be able to verify that a broadcast message originated from a registered UAV, and must be able to do so without communicating with the Authority or Custodian. That is, an attacker cannot create a message that is accepted by a receiver but that cannot be traced to a UAV and its operator.
- **Traceable.** If the Authority meets the requirements for unsealing an identity, then it, with the help of the Custodian, can identify

the operator of the UAV that sent a valid message. This implies that no-one can impersonate an operator to the Authority.

- **Unlinkable.** Neither Authority nor Custodian acting alone, nor an unprivileged receiver, can determine whether two messages from different operational epochs were sent by UAVs with the same operator.

Table 1 summarizes these properties and their relationship to the threat model. Two properties are marked *N/A* to indicate that they do not apply in the threat model. Specifically, with a Corrupt Authority, a protocol cannot be Verifiable or Traceable, since the Authority controls UAV registration and operator identity issuance. Two combinations are marked §4.5: these require protocol extensions described in Section 4.5 to protect against a corrupt Authority and Custodian. Finally, one combination, Verifiable broadcasts under a Corrupt Custodian, is marked *No*. A corrupt Custodian can generate broadcasts from fictitious UAVs that pass verification; this limitation of CAPSID offers a direction for future improvement. We note, however, that a Corrupt Custodian cannot frame a real operator in the extended CAPSID protocol described in Section 4.5.

3.5 Overview

To ensure the authenticity of broadcast flight information, UAVs sign every message. CAPSID uses certificates to establish signing key authenticity and prove that the UAV is registered with the Authority. CAPSID consists of an enrollment phase, where an operator interacts with the Authority and Custodian to obtain the necessary certificates, and an operational phase during which a UAV broadcasts signed flight information messages. We begin with an overview of CAPSID.

3.5.1 Operator registration. An operator must first register with the Authority. The Authority assigns the operator a unique operator identifier (OID) that is used to identify the operator to the Authority. This step follows existing operator registration practices. The result of registration should be credentials allowing the operator establish a secure communication channel (e.g. TLS) with the Authority.

3.5.2 Enrollment. Enrollment in the system consists of two steps: UAV registration with the Authority and flight subscription with the Custodian. To get permission to operate an UAV, an operator must register it with the Authority to obtain a set of epoch certificates (E-certs), one for each operational epoch (UTC day). E-certs are constructed in such a way that they cannot be linked across epochs by anyone except the operator, UAV, or Authority. The operator then takes these E-certs to the Custodian and converts each E-cert into a flight certificate (F-cert) signed by the Custodian. Each

Table 1: CAPSID Security properties and threat models.

Property	Unpr.	Curious		Corrupt	
		Auth.	Cust.	Auth.	Cust.
Verifiable	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	No
Traceable	Yes	Yes	Yes	N/A	§4.5
Unlinkable	Yes	Yes	Yes	§4.5	Yes

F-cert includes a unique flight signing public key generated by the operator: this key is used to sign flight information broadcast messages containing the mandated Remote ID information block. The F-cert, which is sent with the flight information broadcast, proves that the UAV has been properly registered and is permitted to operate. Figure 2 shows this set of transformations, which are explained in detail in Sections 4.1–4.4.

The reason for having two steps—registration with the Authority and subscription with the Custodian—is to break the association between the signing key used to sign flight information broadcasts and the operator’s identity. The Authority creates the E-certs and can associate each E-cert with an operator, but it is the only one that can do so. We cannot use E-certs to establish a signing key for flight information broadcasts, because then the Authority would be able to identify the operator behind each broadcast, something that should only be possible after an explicit unsealing operation.

The Custodian-issued F-certs contain the key used to sign flight information broadcasts. F-certs are constructed in such a way that only the operator, UAV, and Custodian, but not the Authority, can link an F-cert to the E-cert for which it is generated. The process of converting E-certs to F-certs is anonymous if the operator takes precautions not to disclose their identity to the Custodian. E-certs are constructed in a way that it is impractical to link E-certs from the same operator across epochs. However, as noted, the operator must take care to convert each E-cert to an F-cert separately, so the Custodian cannot correlate multiple E-certs using side information.

3.5.3 Broadcast signing. Each F-cert contains a unique signing public key generated by the UAV for use during a given epoch (UTC day). An F-cert attests that this key is associated with a UAV that has been registered with the Authority. The UAV uses this key—called with flight information signing key—to sign flight information broadcasts. In addition to the required message block (signed with the flight information signing key), a UAV also broadcasts its F-cert. A receiver that receives a CAPSID flight information broadcast and the F-cert verifies that (a) the flight information broadcast was signed using the flight information signing key contained in the F-cert, and (b) that the F-cert was signed using the Custodian signing key, a well-known public key. The receiver also checks if the indicated time is the current time (to detect replays) and checks if the epoch of the F-cert is the current or previous epoch; the latter allows for flights that started during the previous epoch.

Both E-certs and F-certs are constructed in such a way that within a given epoch, it is possible to determine if two certificates belong to the same operator. This is allowed by short-term linkability and it makes it possible for any receiver to detect a Sybil attack, where a malicious operator registers many fictitious UAVs and then uses their F-certs to simulate multiple fictitious targets.

3.5.4 Unsealing. Should the Authority need to determine the identity of an operator associated with a set of given CAPSID broadcasts, the Authority takes the collected flight information broadcasts and F-cert to the Custodian. The Custodian ensures that the Authority has met the legal requirements for unsealing an operator’s identity. For example, if the Authority claims that the UAV was operated in a restricted airspace, the Custodian can verify that the coordinates in the broadcast are inside the claimed airspace. Or, if the UAV was used in the commission of a crime, the Custodian can require a

Figure 1: CAPSID protocol workflow.

judicial warrant for unsealing. The Custodian then reveals to the Authority which E-cert was used to generate the presented F-cert. The Authority can then map the E-cert back to the operator to whom the E-cert was issued.

Using a trusted third party—the Custodian—to implement unsealing make it possible to enforce complex legal requirements for unsealing, such as judicial warrants. Given the complex and technologically conservative nature of the US judicial system, it seems difficult to avoid the need for a mutually-trusted Custodian to mediator between the Authority and the privacy rights of operators.

The Custodian can also be charged with producing transparency reports with statistics about the unsealing operations (e.g. total number of unsealed identities in a year).

Finally, it is possible to require the Custodian to destroy records linking F-certs to E-certs after a certain period of time. In CAPSID, F-certs are linked back to E-certs by including information from the E-cert in the F-cert in encrypted form. The encryption is done using a epoch-specific symmetric encryption key. By destroying this key, the Custodian can make it impossible to link F-certs to E-certs for that epoch.

4 CAPSID PROTOCOL

This section described the CAPSID protocol in detail. Sections 4.1–4.4 describe the core CAPSID protocol. Section 4.5 extends the core protocol to provide additional desirable properties, including protection against a corrupt, but non-colluding, Authority and Custodian. Section 5 presents a security analysis of the protocol.

4.1 UAV Registration

The remainder of this section describes enrollment and operational phases in detail. Figure 1 illustrates this workflow and serves as a guide to the description below. Figure 2 details the constructions of certificates and related data structures. An operator initiates the registration process by sending her OID to the UAV and specifying an interval D of epochs for which she wants E-certs (step 1 in Figure 1). In CAPSID, epochs correspond to UTC days and are identified by integers starting from some designated day zero, so $D \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. The Authority may restrict the range of epochs for which it will issue E-certs: for example, the Authority may not issue E-certs for epochs in the past and may not issue E-certs more than some number of days into the future.

Figure 2: Certificate and broadcast construction.

E-CSR construction. For each epoch i in D , the UAV generates a public-private signing key pair. Let K_i^{UE} and κ_i^{UE} denote the public and private keys, respectively, for epoch i . For each epoch i , the UAV creates a **epoch certificate signing request (E-CSR)**:

$$\text{ECSR}(i, \text{OID}, \text{UID}, K_i^{UE}, \kappa_i^{UE}) \equiv (i, \text{OID}, \text{UID}, K_i^{UE}, \sigma_{\text{ecsr}}), \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ecsr} is a digital signature applied to the preceding members of the tuple. That is,

$$\sigma_{\text{ecsr}} = S_{\kappa_i^{UE}}(i || \text{OID} || \text{UID} || K_i^{UE}), \quad (2)$$

where S is the signing function for the digital signature scheme.

The UAV returns the E-CSRs to the operator (2), and the operator sends them to the Authority (3). The Authority verifies ensure that the E-CSRs are well-formed and verifies their signatures. The Authority also checks that the OIDs in the E-CSRs are those of the operator. (Here we use the assumption that the operator has an authenticated channel to the Authority, so the Authority can determine whether it is communicating with the owner of the OID in the E-CSRs.) Finally, the Authority ensures that the E-CSRs are for the current or future epochs.

E-cert construction. The Authority has a public-private key pair K^{Auth} and κ^{Auth} that is used for signing E-certs; we assume that the public key K^{Auth} is well-known to all participants. In addition,

the Authority has a symmetric encryption key κ^{AE} that it uses to encrypt OIDs and UIDs. For each E-CSR, the Authority creates an **epoch certificate (E-cert)**:

$$\text{ECERT}(i, \text{OID}, \text{UID}, K_i^{UE}) \equiv (i, \text{EOID}_i, \text{EUID}_i, K_i^{UE}, \sigma_{\text{ecert}}), \quad (3)$$

where EOID_i and EUID_i are the encrypted OID and UID, respectively, and σ_{ecert} is a digital signature applied to the preceding members of the tuple using the Authority's signing key κ^{Auth} . That is,

$$\sigma_{\text{ecert}} = S_{\kappa^{\text{Auth}}}(i || \text{EOID}_i || \text{EUID}_i || K_i^{UE}). \quad (4)$$

EOID and EUID construction. The encrypted OIDs and UIDs, termed EOIDs and EUIDs and denoted EOID_i and EUID_i , are produced by encrypting the OID and UID using a tweaked block cipher [28] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EOID}_i &\equiv \tilde{E}_{\kappa^{\text{AE}}}(0 || i, \text{OID}), \\ \text{EUID}_i &\equiv \tilde{E}_{\kappa^{\text{AE}}}(1 || \text{EOID}_i, \text{UID}). \end{aligned}$$

That is, EOID_i is tweaked using epoch number i , prefixed with a 0 bit, and EUID_i is tweaked using EOID_i prefixed with 1 bit. Tweaking ensures that the EUID depends on the UID and OID, preventing an attacker who knows one UID to EUID mapping from learning another operator's UAV identifier. The prefix bits ensure the tweak spaces are disjoint, preventing a similar attack.⁵

This construction of EOIDs ensures that two UAVs registered by an operator will have the same EOID in their E-certs for epoch i , which will make it possible to detect an operator operating more than one UAV at the same time (which is prohibited by the FAA). At the same time, because the EUID is tweaked using the EOID, it is impractical for anyone but the Authority to use the knowledge of one operator's UIDs and EUIDs to learn anything about another operator's UIDs.

The Authority sends the E-certs to the operator (4). An E-cert allows an operator to obtain an F-cert for the corresponding epoch. The epoch signing key K_i^{UE} included in the certificate allows an operator to later prove to the Custodian that the E-cert is issued to her, without revealing her identity.

4.2 Flight Subscription

In the flight subscription step, the operator converts E-certs obtained from the Authority into F-certs one-to-one. An F-cert gives an operator permission to operate a UAV during a given epoch. An operator initiates the subscription process by sending the E-certs obtained from the Authority to the UAV (5).

F-CSR construction. The UAV uses the E-certs to create flight certificate signing requests that it then returns to the operator (6). For each E-cert epoch i , the UAV generates a new flight public-private signing key pair, K_i^{UF} and κ_i^{UF} . It then constructs the **flight**

⁵Note that in the given construction, the tweak size is one bit longer than the block size. For practical constructions, it is more convenient to have the tweak and block size be the same. While our security proof assumes the "inconvenient" tweak size, we believe it is safe to use i with its highest order bit forced to 0 as the tweak for the EOID, and EOID with its highest order bit forced to 1 as the tweak for the EUID.

certificate signing request (F-CSR):

$$\text{FCSR}((i, \text{EOID}_i, \text{EUID}_i, K_i^{\text{UE}}, \sigma_{\text{ecert}}), \kappa_i^{\text{UE}}, K_i^{\text{UF}}, \kappa_i^{\text{UF}}) \equiv \quad (5)$$

$$\underbrace{((i, \text{EOID}_i, \text{EUID}_i, K_i^{\text{UE}}, \sigma_{\text{ecert}}), K_i^{\text{UF}}, \sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UE}}, \sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UF}})}_{\text{E-cert}},$$

where $\sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UE}}$ and $\sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UF}}$ are digital signatures applied to the preceding members of the tuple. That is,

$$\sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UE}} = S_{\kappa_i^{\text{UE}}}(i || \text{EOID}_i || \text{EUID}_i || K_i^{\text{UE}} || \sigma_{\text{ecert}} || K_i^{\text{UF}}), \text{ and}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UF}} = S_{\kappa_i^{\text{UF}}}(i || \text{EOID}_i || \text{EUID}_i || K_i^{\text{UE}} || \sigma_{\text{ecert}} || K_i^{\text{UF}} || \sigma_{\text{fcsr}}^{\text{UE}}).$$

The F-CSR contains the original E-cert for epoch i issued by the Authority, the new flight signing public key K_i^{UF} generated by the operator and two signatures. The first signature, applied to the preceding members, uses the epoch signing key κ_i^{UE} , the public key for which was established in the E-cert. This serves as proof that the subject of the E-cert is requesting the associated F-cert. The last signature, over all preceding members including the previous signature, proves ownership of the flight signing key κ_i^{UF} .

F-cert construction. To obtain a F-cert for epoch i , the operator sends the F-CSR for epoch i to the Custodian (7). The Custodian ensures that the F-CSR is well-formed and verifies all signatures. The Custodian also ensures that the epoch i is not before the current epoch. The Custodian's process of generating an F-cert mirrors the Authority's process for generating an E-cert. The Custodian has a public-private key pair K^{Cust} and κ^{Cust} that is used for signing F-certs; we assume that the public key K^{Cust} is well-known to all participants. In addition, the Custodian has a symmetric encryption key κ^{CF} that it uses to encrypt EOIDs and EUIDs. For each F-CSR, the Custodian creates a **flight certificate (F-cert)**:

$$\text{FCERT}(i, \text{EOID}_i, \text{EUID}_i, K_i^{\text{UF}}) \equiv (i, \text{FOID}_i, \text{FUID}_i, K_i^{\text{UF}}, \sigma_{\text{fcert}}), \quad (6)$$

where FOID_i and FUID_i are the encrypted EOID and EUID, respectively, and σ_{fcert} is a digital signature applied to the preceding members of the tuple using the Custodian's signing key κ^{Cust} . That is,

$$\sigma_{\text{fcert}} = S_{\kappa^{\text{Cust}}}(i || \text{FOID}_i || \text{FUID}_i || K_i^{\text{UF}}). \quad (7)$$

The Custodian sends the F-certs to the operator (8).

FOID and FUID construction. The EOID and EUID from the F-CSR encrypted a second time to form the FOID and FUID, which we denoted FOID_i and FUID_i . They are produced by encrypting the EOID and EUID using a tweaked block cipher [28] as follows:

$$\text{FOID}_i \equiv \tilde{E}_{\kappa^{\text{CF}}}(0 || i, \text{EOID}_i),$$

$$\text{FUID}_i \equiv \tilde{E}_{\kappa^{\text{CF}}}(1 || \text{FOID}_i, \text{EUID}_i).$$

That is, FOID_i is tweaked using epoch number i , prefixed with a 0 bit, and FUID_i is tweaked using FOID_i prefixed with 1 bit. This construction of FOIDs and FUIDs from EOIDs and EUIDs mirrors the construction of EOIDs and EUIDs from OIDs and UIDs. This ensures that two UAVs registered by an operator will have the same FOID in their F-certs any any given epoch, making it possible to detect a pilot-operator operating more than one UAV at the same time (prohibited by the FAA). Note that the Custodian can map an FOID to its corresponding EOID, but not to its OID. The Authority can map an EOID to its OID, but not an FOID to EOID or OID. A UAV includes an F-cert appropriate for the epoch with its flight

information broadcasts which contains its FOID; however, neither Authority nor Custodian alone can link an FOID to an OID.

Both FOIDs and FUIDs are encrypted using a tweaked block cipher in the same way as EOIDs and EUIDs. If the FOID and FUID were encrypted without tweaking, an unprivileged receiver—one that is neither the Authority nor the Custodian—would not be able to learn anything useful about the original OID and UID. Using a tweaked block cipher prevents FOID inference attacks by a corrupt Authority, as discussed in Section 5.3.

Protecting against F-CSR correlation by a Custodian. If an operator were to submit all F-CSRs to the Custodian in a single batch, the Custodian would be able to link the issued F-certs across epochs, violating the long-term unlinkability property. To protect against such a Custodian, the operator must submit F-CSRs to the Custodian individually, at different times, from different IP addresses, and without additional information that could be used to fingerprint operators. This can be built into the operator's software agent: We envision operators using a smartphone app or desktop application to manage their certificates; such a software agent could automatically submit F-CSRs to a Custodian using Tor [21] at random times.

4.3 Flight Information Broadcasts

The operator sends each F-cert she obtains to the UAV (9). An F-cert establishes a flight public signing key that a UAV uses during a given epoch. More precisely, a UAV selects the key corresponding to the epoch at the start of its flight and continues to use the same key for the duration of the flight. For small UAVs that are the subject of Remote ID regulation, the duration of a flight is much less than a day, or say the duration of an epoch. Therefore, at any given time, a UAV may be operating using the current or previous epoch's F-cert.

Each flight information broadcast (10), containing message elements listed in Section 2.1, is signed using the flight signing key κ_i^{UF} , where i is the epoch at the start of the flight. In addition to the flight information broadcast, a UAV must also broadcast its active F-cert, which contains the corresponding public key K_i^{UF} . Alternatively, a UAV can concatenate the F-cert with the flight information message data and sign the combined message, as shown in Figure 2. If the F-cert is broadcast separately, the protocol should provide a way to easily identify the corresponding F-cert. For example, the session ID element could be set to FUID_i .

Receiver verification. When a receiver receives a flight information broadcast and a F-cert,⁶ the receiver ensures that the message and F-cert are well formed and then verifies two signatures: the signature on the flight information message using the flight signing public key K_i^{UF} from the F-cert, and the Custodian's signature on the F-cert using K^{Cust} . (The result of F-cert verification can be cached.) The receiver also checks the time (element (g)) is correct to within some allowed tolerance, and that the epoch of the F-cert is either the current or previous epoch.

Non-compliance. A UAV that fails the above receiver checks is declared non-compliant. There is nothing CAPSID—or any other protocol—can do to remedy non-compliance; it is equivalent to the UAV operating without a Remote ID transmitter. What is important,

⁶If the flight information and F-cert are sent separately, we assume both are sent periodically. A receiver that receives one but not the other in some period of time should consider the UAV non-compliant.

however, is that non-compliance can be detected by any unprivileged receiver without needing to communicate with the Authority or Custodian. The FAA’s Remote ID protocol (with or without session IDs) does not provide a way to detect non-compliance. The recently proposed ARID protocol [38] requires receiver communication with the Authority to verify compliance, while its successor, A²RID [41], does not.

4.4 Unsealing

Within an operational epoch, CAPSID allows any receiver to link multiple transmissions from the same UAV. Across operational epochs, however, CAPSID makes it infeasible to track UAVs and their operators. CAPSID provides a mechanism for the Authority to unseal the identity of a UAV and its operator with the help of the Custodian. The Custodian can decrypt the FOID and FUID in an F-cert and provide the corresponding EOID and EUID to the Authority. The Authority can in turn decrypt those to get the OID and UID.

Meeting the requirements for unsealing. The Custodian should only unseal a FOID-FUID pair if the Authority has met the legal requirements for doing so. CAPSID does not prescribe what these requirements should be nor what form they should take. Having a separate trusted third party—the Custodian—in charge of unsealing permits maximum flexibility in what form policy should take. The privacy guarantees of CAPSID rely crucially on the integrity of the Custodian. If the Custodian colludes with the Authority, or an adversary is allowed to compromise both, all of CAPSID’s privacy guarantees evaporate. It is essential, therefore, that any practical implementation of CAPSID address this non-technical requirement. In Section 6.1 we discuss potential candidates for the role of Custodian. (The role of the Authority is played by the FAA and its counterparts in other jurisdictions.) In this work, we assume that the Custodian does not collude with the Authority (Section 3.2).

Transparency. In addition to enforcing unsealing requirements, the Custodian can be used to provide process transparency, akin to the transparency reports provided by some Internet service companies [18, 22, 30]. For example, the Custodian could report the number of operator identities unsealed in a given year, or other statistics that might signal abuse of the system by the Authority. Even in a jurisdiction where the Custodian cannot refuse an unsealing request, providing transparency reports still fulfills an important role.

4.5 Extensions

4.5.1 Custodian ledger. In the Corrupt Authority and Corrupt Custodian threat models, the Authority and Custodian are not required to follow the prescribed CAPSID protocol. (We do not, however, allow Authority and Custodian to collude.) The core protocol described so far is vulnerable to two kinds of attacks.

First, a Corrupt Authority can defeat the non-linkability property by creating an E-cert for any operator’s OID (signed using an operator epoch key pair generated by the Authority), creating the corresponding F-CSR, and then submitting the F-CSR to the Custodian. The Custodian would dutifully issue the corresponding F-cert, revealing the targeted operator’s FOID to the corrupt Authority; this would allow the corrupt Authority to identify that operator’s

broadcasts. Since all identities are managed by the Authority, the Custodian has no way to verify that the submitted F-CSR is from the operator, and not a corrupt Authority. While the Custodian cannot prevent such an impersonation attack, it can make it possible to detect it using a certificate transparency mechanism. Specifically, for every issued F-cert, the Custodian publishes a record of all valid F-CSRs for which it issued an F-cert to an append-only public ledger. This allows any operator to detect F-certs being issued for her EOID by the Custodian.

The core protocol also allows a corrupt Custodian to frame an innocent operator by lying about the result of unsealing. This is because the Custodian unseals an identity by decrypting the FOID and FUID from an F-cert to reveal the corresponding EOID and EUID. However, there is no way to verify that the EOID and EUID produced by the Custodian correspond to the original FOID and FUID: a corrupt Custodian could claim that the provided FOID and FUID decrypt to another operator’s EOID and EUID. The solution to this problem also relies on the Custodian publishing a public append-only ledger of transactions. Specifically, the Custodian maintains an append-only ledger made available to the public listing every transaction. In addition to the necessary ledger linkage, each F-cert issuance record consists of the following:

- (1) Timestamp of the transaction,
- (2) The epoch number, EOID, and EUID from the F-CSR, and
- (3) A cryptographic commitment to the the issued F-cert.

The ledger serves two main purposes. First, it allows any operator to monitor the ledger for her EOID to ensure that the only F-certs issued for her EOID are those she requested. This prevents a corrupt Authority from obtaining F-certs for a operator’s EOID, thereby linking EOIDs to FOIDs. (An unprivileged user cannot do this because F-CSRs contain an E-cert signed by the Authority, and we assume that an honest authority verifies operator identities when issuing E-certs.) It is important that the operator checks the ledger both going forward after obtaining her E-cert from the Authority, to prevent future linking attacks, and going backward, to prevent a corrupt Authority from assigning a previously FOID-linked EOID to the operator.⁷

The second purpose of the ledger is to ensure that the Custodian cannot lie about an unsealed identity. When the Custodian issues the F-cert to the operator, it also opens the F-cert commitment in the ledger to the operator (but *only* to the operator). This allows the operator to verify that the F-cert she obtained from the operator is tied to her EOID in the ledger. When the Custodian unseals an identity for the Authority, it also opens the F-cert commitment to the Authority. The Authority verifies that the F-cert is indeed linked to the EOID. It is important for operators to monitor the ledger to ensure that any F-certs issued to their EOIDs are legitimate, and to immediately dispute any illegitimate F-certs.

⁷If an operator observes that the EOID in an E-cert issued by an Authority already appears in the ledger, she can refrain from using the E-cert, preventing any linking. It is harder to protect against a corrupt Authority fraudulently requesting an F-cert with an operator’s EOID after issuing the real E-cert to the operator with the same EOID. Note that the Custodian does not issue F-certs retroactively, so a corrupt Authority could only obtain a F-cert for the current or future epoch. If an operator checks the ledger before using an F-cert, a corrupt Authority has a maximum 24-hour window in which it can request another F-cert for the operator’s EOID in a given epoch. Additional mechanisms could be put into place to prevent attacks in this 24-hour window.

4.5.2 Operator key loss and theft. Operators are expected to manage two sets of private keys: the UAV epoch signing keys $\langle \kappa_i^{UE} \rangle$ and the UAV flight signing keys $\langle \kappa_i^{UF} \rangle$. Only one of the two sets of keys needs to exist for any given epoch: an operator can generate UAV flight signing keys $\langle \kappa_i^{UF} \rangle$ immediately prior to generating the F-CSR, and can destroy the UAV epoch signing keys $\langle \kappa_i^{UE} \rangle$ after she obtains the corresponding F-cert from the Custodian. Although nominally, these keys “belong” to the UAV, we expect that in practice, these keys will be managed by an operator’s software agent (a desktop, mobile, or Web application), and loaded onto the UAV before flight. Loading keys on the UAV as needed, rather than storing them on the UAV, prevents key loss if the UAV is lost or stolen. The operator’s software agent should follow good practices for managing keying material, namely storing secret keys encrypted, decrypting keys in memory only, and transferring keys to the UAV re-encrypted using an ephemeral encryption key generated for this purpose only. These precautions notwithstanding, because in many cases operators and individuals with a hobbyist interest in UAVs, we expect key loss to be a common occurrence.

In the event of key destruction, the operator can simply repeat the UAV registration and flight subscription process (Sections 4.1 and 4.2), and operate using the new keys. Even if the operator lies about the keys being lost, the deterministic nature of OID to EIOD and EOID to FOID encryption means that the new F-certs will have the same FOIDs as the F-certs that were generated (or would have been generated) using the lost keys. Thus, an operator will not be able to use both keys at the same time without detection. (See also the discussion of swarm attacks in Section 5.2.)

In the event an operator’s keys are stolen, it becomes necessary to revoke the stolen keys, both to prevent their use and to prevent the original operator from being blamed for the thief’s actions using the stolen keys. Multiple revocation mechanisms are possible. The simplest is operator-issued (PGP-style) revocation: the operator can issue a revocation statement signed using the original (now stolen) key and publishing the revocation to a common public revocation list, which could be maintained by the Custodian. An operator, via her software agent, should pre-generate the revocation statement, or *revocation certificate* on PGP terminology, so that it can be published if the underlying key is stolen.

Revocation can also be initiated by the Authority or Custodian (X.509 style). In the first case, the operator can request the Authority to revoke an issued E-cert. The Authority can then send the revocation directly to the Custodian to inform the Custodian not to issue any F-certs for the revoked E-certs. In the second case, if the Custodian has already issued an F-cert (either to the original operator or to the thief), the Custodian can issue a revocation for the F-cert. Revoked F-certs should be published in a common revocation list maintained by the Custodian. Receivers that want to detect revoked certificates use should keep up to date with issued revocations.

4.5.3 Forced data expiration. The ability to unseal identities can be limited in time. To do this, the Custodian should use a different symmetric encryption key κ^{CF} for each epoch. These keys can then be destroyed after some period of time, making it impossible to decrypt old FOIDs and FUIDs.

4.5.4 Fleet operators. Up to this point, we have largely focused on the case of a hobbyist pilot-operator. Our deterministic encryption of the FOID, for example, is designed to allow anyone to detect an operator flying multiple UAVs simultaneously (Section 5.2). Some operators, however, may need to operate a fleet of UAVs. There are two ways to handle this. First, an operator can be assigned multiple OIDs, to be used, for example, to assign a unique OID to each pilot. Such operators could be subject to additional oversight to prevent misuse. The second option is to specify in the F-cert the number of simultaneous UAVs that an operator can have in the air. Multiple UAVs operating simultaneously with a single FOID would not be considered a violation so long as the number of UAVs does not exceed the maximum listed in the F-certs for each.

4.5.5 Miscellaneous attacks. An attacker could intercept broadcast messages from one UAVs at one location and immediately re-broadcast them from another UAV. However, such an attack is easy to detect, as the position and velocity information contained in the broadcast would not match the actual position of the re-broadcasting UAV.

An attacker can spoof a GPS signal and cause the UAV to misbehave and broadcast erroneous information. GPS spoofing is a complex problem not unique to CAPSID; we refer the reader to the survey by Psiaki and Humphreys for a discussion of this issue [31].

5 SECURITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we prove that CAPSID satisfies the security properties enumerated in Section 3.4. Specifically, in Section 5.1, we use the cryptographic protocol verification tool ProVerif to show that CAPSID broadcasts are verifiable and traceable (in the sense of Section 3.4). Then, in Section 5.3, we prove that CAPSID provides operator non-linkability across operational epochs.

5.1 Verifiability and Traceability

We use ProVerif [8], a cryptographic protocol verification tool, to show that CAPSID messages are verifiable and traceable. The ProVerif input file can be downloaded from:

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13619881>

5.1.1 Problem modeling. ProVerif’s support for standard cryptographic operations is well-adapted to modeling CAPSID. Here we describe the main objects and processes in our model, as well as how to modeled attacker capabilities.

Constructors and reductions. To model CAPSID, we first define ProVerif constructors and reductions for the following objects:

- *Tweakable block cipher.* We model encryption and decryption in the usual way done in ProVerif [9, Sec. 4.2.5]. We model prepending 0 or 1 to the plaintext (to form the EOID, EUID, FOID, and FUID) by defining two distinct encryption functions. We model the tweak as an additional key-like input.
- *E-CSRs.* We model an E-CSR following Eq. 4.1 as a constructor of arity 4 taking the epoch, OID, UID, and signing secret key. The signing secret key represents the signing public key (which can be derived from the secret key) and the signature σ_{ecsr} (Eq. 2). The corresponding reduction returns the epoch, OID, and UID. We do not model a CSR signed using a different

key, as we assume all consumers of the E-CSR will verify the signature on the CSR using the enclosed public key.

- *E-certs*. We model an E-cert following Eq. 3 as a constructor of arity 5 taking the epoch, EOID, EUID, signing public key K_i^{UE} and the Authority signing private key κ^{Auth} . The private key models the Authority's signature σ_{cert} (Eq. 4) on the certificate. The corresponding reduction takes the Authority signing public key K^{Auth} and an E-cert and returns the first four elements of the constructor if the public signing key provided to the reduction is public signing key that corresponds to the secret key provided to the constructor.
- *F-CSRs*. We model an F-CSR following Eq. 5 as a constructor of arity 3 taking the E-cert, and secret signing keys κ_i^{UE} and κ_i^{UF} . The first secret key in the constructor represents the signature σ_{fcsr}^{UE} ; the second secret key represents the signing public key K_i^{UF} and the signature σ_{fcsr}^{UF} . The reduction checks the Authority's signature on the enclosed E-cert and the signature σ_{fcsr}^{UE} . We do not model checking the signature σ_{fcsr}^{UF} because we assume all consumers of the F-CSR will check σ_{fcsr}^{UF} against the enclosed key K_i^{UF} .
- *F-certs*. We model an F-cert following Eq. 6 in a manner similar to E-certs.
- *Broadcasts*. We model a flight information broadcast using a constructor of arity 3, consisting of an arbitrary message (bitstring), an F-cert, and the signing secret key κ_i^{UF} (standing for the signature on the broadcast made using this key). The reduction checks the F-cert signature and broadcast signature and returns the F-cert and message.

In addition, we model the ledger (Sec. 4.5.1) as a table visible and appendable, but not modifiable, by the attacker.

Processes. We model an honest Authority and honest Custodian as processes, along with unlimited unprivileged receivers, honest operators, and unsealing processes. The unsealing process has access to the secret keys of the Authority and Custodian and attempts to unseal every broadcast. (Since we are not concerned with verifying Unlinkability, the unsealing process has the keys of both.) The unsealing process accepts an F-cert only if it appears in the ledger. This is to ensure that an operator has a chance to dispute any F-certs issued for her EOID, as discussed in Section 4.5.1.

Attacker capabilities. The attacker modeled by the ProVerif model of CAPSID has the following capabilities:

- *Unlimited Authority and Custodian interaction*. The attacker can have unlimited number of interactions with an honest Authority and honest Custodian, including obtaining E-certs and F-certs under multiple attacker-controller operator identities.
- *Full access to broadcast channel*. The attacker can observe flight information broadcasts made by operators and make new broadcasts.
- *Limited control of legitimate operators*. The attacker can cause any number of legitimate operators to request E-certs and F-certs for any epoch and UID. The attacker can observe the E-cert issued to these operators. After obtaining an F-cert, each controller operator begins making broadcasts (also observable by attacker). The attacker *cannot* cause these operators to

deviate from the correct protocol and does *not* have access to their keys.

- *Compromised Custodian*. Optionally, controlled by commenting out several lines of code, we can model a corrupt Custodian. To do this, we provide the attacker the Custodian's secret keys and give the attacker access to the (normally secure) channel between operators and the Custodian.

In all cases in the ProVerif model, we assume an honest Authority. As already noted, broadcast Verifiability and Traceability is not meaningful if the Authority, which manages all identities, is corrupt.

5.1.2 Verification queries. We issue three verification queries to ProVerif, described below.

Query 1: Verifiable broadcasts. We query the assertion that, if a broadcast is accepted by a receiver, then (a) the F-cert included in the broadcast has been issued by the Custodian, and (b) an E-cert containing the epoch, EOID and EUID, where the FOID decrypts to the EOID and the FUID decrypts to the EUID using the Custodian key, has been issued by the Authority. This query succeeds in the honest Custodian model and fails in the Corrupt Custodian model.

Query 2: Traceable broadcasts. We create an operator with a distinguished operator with an OID known to the attacker. This operator is under limited attacker control, as described above. We query the assertion that, if a broadcast appearing to be from the distinguished user is accepted by a receiver, then the distinguished operator must have sent the message. This query establishes that an unprivileged user cannot impersonate another. The query succeeds in the honest Custodian model and fails in the Corrupt Custodian model.

Query 3: Impersonation-resistant broadcasts. The third query tests the assertion that if a broadcast is traced to an operator (by the Authority) and the operator has accepted the F-cert, then the operator must have sent the message. Accepting an F-cert is an event generated by an honest operator when it receives a valid F-cert from the Custodian (or an attacker impersonating the Custodian) and observes the F-cert committed to the ledger. We do not explicitly model an operator checking the ledger for her own EOID. Instead, we assume that once an operator has received an EOID from the Authority, she will ensure that no F-certs have been issued for that EOID and will continually monitor the ledger for it. Assuming that all operators behave this way, accepting an F-cert signals the point after which we assume that any attempts to use the EOID by someone else will be detected in the ledger. Note that the Authority only attributes a broadcast to an operator if the EOID and EUID provided by the Custodian appear in the ledger alongside a commitment to the F-cert opened by the Custodian. This ensures that attribution of a broadcast requires the F-cert to appear in the ledger; by assumption, the operator ensures that any F-certs appearing on the ledger that it did not request are disputed.

5.2 Spoofed UAV Swarm Resistance

As we have shown above, a miscreant cannot impersonate another operator or create another operator identity. However, this does not prevent a miscreant from registering as an operator and sending flight information broadcasts with incorrect information. (We do not model this kind of attack in ProVerif.) In particular, an attacker

who has obtained an F-cert legitimately can make a receiver believe that there is a UAV is at some location, even when there is no UAV there. Although the flight information message can be linked to the miscreant operator after unsealing, the damage is already done. Such a spoofing attack is very hard to detect without examining the transmission at the physical layer, for example, by using multiple receivers to triangulate the transmitter. A smartphone WiFi or Bluetooth receiver, however, is unlikely to be capable of such signal discrimination. It is desirable, however, to limit the damage an attacker who is willing to “burn” her identity can do.

One class of attack that can be especially damaging is an attacker spoofing multiple UAVs. (In the context of ADS-B spoofing, for example, McCallie *et al.* [1] view this as a distinct kind of attack from single target spoofing.) Spoofing multiple UAVs increases the load on the victim and allows an attacker to affect a greater area. While an attacker could try to cover a large area with a single spoofed UAV by changing its position rapidly, such an attack is easy to detect. Spoofing multiple UAVs simultaneously allows the attacker to plausibly appear at multiple locations. A CAPSID receiver can detect that such a spoofed swarm attack is taking place using the FOID field in the F-cert, which will show that multiple apparent UAVs are all registered to a single operator. The same mechanism also allows a receiver to detect multiple operators using the same OID in the same area.

5.3 Operator Non-linkability

Flight information broadcasts consists of a flight information block (see Section 2.1), a digital signature over that block, and the F-cert of the operator (containing the signing key). In CAPSID, the flight information block does not include element (a), the identity of the aircraft, however, other information contained in the block, such as area of operations, could be used to link operators. No protocol can protect against such linking, as that information is necessary for tracking a UAV in flight. CAPSID ensures that no *additional* information, allowing an attacker to link an operator across sessions, is leaked. Specifically, we show that the E-certs and F-certs used by an operator cannot be linked across epochs.

Formally, we construct a *non-linkability experiment* challenging an adversary to identify which of two possible OID and UID pairs, provided by an adversary, was used to create an E-cert. (Or which of two possible EOID and EUID pairs was used to create an F-cert.) The experiment is styled after the indistinguishability under chosen plaintext attack experiment used for encryption schemes.

The construction and proof appear in Appendix A.

5.3.1 Corrupt Authority. A corrupt Authority can create fictitious operators and UAVs, create F-CSRs for them, and submit the F-CSRs to the (honest) Custodian, who will then issue the corresponding F-cert, provided the signatures are correct. For a given real operator, a corrupt Authority can insert arbitrary EOID and EUID values into the requested E-cert—an operator has no way to confirm they were constructed properly. (An operator can ensure that the epoch values i and public keys K_i^{UE} match those in the E-CSR.) The operator will then create an F-CSR based on the E-cert and send it to the Custodian to obtain an F-cert. The corrupt Authority cannot see the operator’s communication with the Custodian. The operator will then use the F-cert provided by the Custodian and include it

in her flight information broadcasts. Thus, for fictitious operators, the Authority can generate their EOIDs and EUIDs as well as link their the EOIDs to FOIDs and their EUIDs to their FUIDs. For real operators, the Authority provides them their EOIDs and EUIDs, but cannot observe the F-certs returned by the Custodian. A corrupt Authority could, however, submit real operators’ EOIDs and EUIDs to the Custodian to obtain the corresponding FOIDs and FUIDs, which would allow it to link those users. CAPSID protects against this attack by having the Custodian publish a public append-only ledger of issued EOIDs, allowing any operator to observe that an impersonation attempt took place. An operator that detects this, can stop using F-certs for the affected epochs, and can report the impersonation attempt.

The Authority might learn, through some other channels, some real users’ FOIDs and FUIDs for some subset of epochs. We show in Appendix A.4, however, that this information does not allow the corrupt Authority to learn anything about those operators’ identity during other epochs.

5.3.2 Corrupt Custodian. A corrupt Custodian can create fictitious operators and UAVs, create E-CSRs for them, and submit the E-CSRs to the (honest) Authority, who will then issue the corresponding E-cert. The corrupt Custodian can then simulate the real process of generating the corresponding F-cert. For real operators, a corrupt Custodian can insert arbitrary FOIDs and FUIDs into their F-certs: operators have no way of knowing whether they were formed correctly. However, there is no benefit to doing so, as the corrupt Custodian can already map FOIDs to EOIDs and FUIDs to EUIDs, and vice versa.

The Custodian might learn, through some other channels, some real users’ EOIDs and EUIDs for some subset of epochs. We show in Appendix A.4, however, that this information does not allow the corrupt Custodian to learn anything about those operators’ identity during other epochs.

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Candidates for the Role of Custodian

The privacy guarantees of CAPSID depend crucially on the availability of the Custodian, a partially-trusted third party. Unfortunately, third parties are few and far between in this world. The Authority must trust the Custodian to unseal identities when required, while operators trust the Custodian to protect their interest and only reveal identities to the Authority when it meets the legal requirements. Who could reasonably play the part?

Another government agency. One natural candidate for the role of Custodian might be another government agency. As another agency of the same government, the Authority should trust it to execute its duties faithfully. From the operators’ point of view, putting another government agency may seem like having the fox guard the hen house. In the United States, there are cases where one government agency is charged with protecting information from another. For example, the Aviation Safety Reporting System (ASRS) was established by the FAA in 1975 to collect voluntary anonymous reports of aviation safety incidents from pilots, air traffic controllers, and other aviation personnel. The FAA transferred operation of the ASRS to the National Aeronautics and Space

Administration (NASA), an independent federal agency: “FAA determined that ASRP effectiveness would be greatly enhanced if NASA, rather than the FAA, accomplished the receipt, processing, and analysis of raw data. This would ensure the anonymity of the reporter and of all parties involved in a reported occurrence or incident ...” [13]. Since 2001, NASA also runs the Patient Safety Reporting System (PSRS), an analog of ASRS for medical incidents. The reasoning for having NASA administer the same: “NASA is an independent, respected research organization that does not have a regulatory or enforcement interest. It can therefore serve as an objective, trustworthy custodian of reports submitted by hospital personnel. The ASRS has provided this guarantee to the aviation community and over 850,000 reports without ever violating a reporter’s confidentiality. NASA can provide the same service to the medical community” [12]. Given its experience with the ASRS and PSRS, we believe that NASA may be a good candidate to operate as a Custodian in the United States.

In the United States, many federal agencies have an Office of Inspector General (OIG) whose is to “to prevent and detect waste, fraud, and abuse relating to their agency’s programs and operations ...” [15]. An Office of Inspector General, in the FAA or in another agency of the United States may also be a candidate for the role.

A UAV pilot or industry association. An association UAV operators or a trade organization of businesses using UAVs may be in a better position to gain operators’ trust as a custodian of their records. However, such an organization may not be well-equipped to continuously operate an online service or may lack the funding to do so. The Authority may also be reluctant to depend on an outside organization in its law enforcement.

UAV manufacturers. Finally, a consortium of UAV manufacturers could provide a Custodian service. UAV manufacturers benefit directly from increased UAV ownership, and are well-incentivized to allay the privacy concerns of operators. From the Authority’s point of view, UAV manufacturers are also motivated to comply with government regulations, so are likely to comply with legal requests.

6.2 Hardware Performance Requirements

Broadcast signing operations are carried out on the UAV, which may be computationally limited. CAPSID is designed using standard cryptographic primitives for which optimized implementations are available, making it easy to implement on most UAVs. Although we have not implemented a UAV receiver, we offer the following back-of-the-envelope analysis to justify our claim. CAPSID requires generating an asymmetric signature once for each broadcast, for which ECDSA as the natural choice. SEGGER Microcontroller Systems, for example, advertises an ECDSA implementation that can generate a P-256 signature in under 150 ms on a 216 MHz STM32F746 Arm-based microcontroller [36]. (For reference, the popular Pixhawk X6 autopilot uses an STM32H753 microcontroller running at 480 MHz [23].) 150 ms fits well within the required time budget of one broadcast per second required by Remote ID.

6.3 Trusted Hardware for Remote ID

CAPSID assumes that there is no trust boundary between operator and her UAV, and that the UAV is an agent of the operator. An

alternative model for a system like CAPSID would be to use tamper-proof hardware with an attested key installed by the manufacturer. The Authority would certify each manufacturer, establishing a chain of trust from Authority to UAV. The FAA already requires Remote ID transmitters be tamper-proof (14 CFR 89.310), however, as noted earlier, without flight information broadcast authentication, an operator can create their own transmitter capable of arbitrary behavior. Switching to a trusted transmitter model could simplify some aspects of the protocol, but runs the risk of creating closed, unverified implementations. One direction for future work is to investigate how trusted hardware platforms could be used to build a CAPSID-like system with stronger guarantees.

7 RELATED WORK

UAV Remote ID. Closest to our work are two protocols Anonymous Remote ID (ARID) [39] and its successor A²RID [42], both of which are intended to solve the UAV remote identification problem. ARID broadcasts are not verifiable by an unprivileged receiver, while A²RID [42] are. Both protocols provide non-linkability by an unprivileged operator (the *miscreant operator* threat model in our terminology). In contrast to CAPSID, both protocols assume a fully trusted authority (called *Trusted Authority* in ARID and *Unmanned Service Supplier* in A²RID) and provide no protection against identity tracking by the authority. In addition, neither protocol provides stable short-term identifiers. This makes it harder for a receiver to track a UAV during flight. It also allows an attacker to spoof a swarm of (traceable) UAVs.

ADS-B. Manned aircraft use a system called Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) that provides remote identification and position reporting to augment secondary surveillance radar. Aircraft flying above 10,000 feet above mean sea level and in airspace around large airports are required to make ADS-B broadcasts. In its requirements for Remote ID, the FAA explicitly required that UAVs *not* use ADS-B, presumably to avoid possible interference with manned aircraft. ADS-B transmitters are assigned a unique 24-bit ICAO identifier that they use to identify themselves. Like Remote ID, ADS-B broadcasts are not verifiable and provide no non-linkability. Numerous schemes have been proposed for authenticated (verifiable and traceable) but not unlinkable ADS-B; see, for example, the proposal by Cook [14].

Asarai *et al.* [2] proposed the Hierarchical Anonymous Certificateless Authentication (HACA) that provides ADS-B broadcast non-linkability by unprivileged receivers. Like CAPSID, it splits the authority into a Key Generation Center (KGC) and Trace Authority (TA). However, as with protocols like ARID above and the VANET protocols cited below, at least one of the authorities, in this case the TA, is fully trusted and can unseal any identity without oversight.

VANETs. The idea of verifiable, traceable, and unlinkable broadcast messages has also been explored in the context of Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs). For example, Shao *et al.* [37] propose an anonymous authentication protocol for vehicles using a group signature scheme. The authority is split between a Central Authority (CA) and Tracing Manager (CM), roughly equivalent

to our Authority and Custodian. However, their TM can unilaterally reveal the identity of any vehicle. Most VANET threat models assume a trusted authority that can unseal identities unilaterally [4, 16, 25, 27, 29, 33, 37, 40]. (In contrast, CAPSID is motivated by concerns over government surveillance and explicitly aims to minimize trust the central authorities.)

The \mathcal{V} -tokens system of Schaub *et al.* [35] further splits the roles of identity certification, anonymous identifier issuance, and de-anonymization between multiple parties. Their system consist of certificate authority (CA), one or more pseudonym providers (PPs), resolution authorities (RAs). RAs have the ability to unseal the true identity of vehicles, as known to the CA. RAs use a secret-sharing scheme so that so minimum number of RAs is necessary unseal an identity. In the issuing side, the authors use blind signatures: the CA signs a blinded \mathcal{V} -token, which a PP verifies. The \mathcal{V} -token contains the the permanent vehicle identifier, encrypted using the public key of the RAs. The PP then signs a new public key that the vehicle uses as a pseudonym. Unfortunately, the scheme as described allows an attacker to obtain \mathcal{V} -tokens for other vehicles.⁸ Their scheme also appears to contemplate honest but curious authorities only. However, we believe that blinded signatures and secret-sharing could be used to create an alternative mechanism to CAPSID's.

Fischer *et al.* [20] also propose a scheme using secret sharing and blinded signatures, but does not offer a proof of security; their threat model also appears to assume honest but curious authorities. CoPRA [7] is another system that is designed with untrusted authorities in mind. The protocol does not provide identifiers that are non-linkable by the long-term certificate authority, which issues the permanent vehicle identifiers.⁹ In the context of prior work, CAPSID provides a stronger threat model and a proof of security.

Group signatures. Group signatures are a general cryptographic mechanism that allows members of a pre-defined group to digitally sign messages without revealing the identity of the signer to an unprivileged verifier. A specially privileged authority called the *opener* is allowed to reveal the identity of the signer [6, 10, 11]. (Many of the VANET protocols cited above are, in fact, based on group signature schemes.) It is likely that group signatures could be used as the basis for a private session ID system like CAPSID; for this, the role of opener must be split between two parties. CAPSID provides non-linkability even against corrupt (but non-colluding) authorities. In addition, group signatures do not, by themselves, provide a stable short-term identifier, so additional mechanisms would need to be put into place to create such identifiers.

Identity escrow. Identity escrow is a closely related scheme (to group signatures) that allows one party, the *identifier*, to provide to a *verifier* an anonymous identity that can be linked to a real identity by an *escrow agent*, should the need arise. (Another party, the *issuer*, is responsible for issuing certificates.) As with group signatures, an application of identity escrow schemes to our problem would require splitting the verifier into two parties. Thus, CAPSID can be viewed as a form of identity escrow.

⁸The CA has no way to identify that the true vehicle identifier, encrypted to the RAs' public key, belongs to the requesting vehicle [35, Step (3) in Fig. 1].

⁹The long-term certificate authority receives a hash of the public key in the pseudonym certificate [7, Step 5 in Fig. 3], which would allow it to link observed pseudonym certificates to long-term identifiers.

Summary. In this work, we do not introduce any new cryptographic primitives or assumptions (which may be more psychologically acceptable to some stakeholders). We use symmetric encryption and digital signature schemes for the core protocol; the extended protocol uses a commitment scheme and append-only ledger to provide non-linkability against a corrupt Adversary or corrupt Custodian, and to protect against framing by a corrupt Custodian. In contrast to prior work on UAV and vehicle identification, we provide a stronger threat model and a proof of security.

8 CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented CAPSID, a proposal for a private session ID mechanism for small UAV remote identification. CAPSID provides broadcast authentication and protects operator privacy even against a corrupt authority that aims to track operators and UAVs. To achieve this, we rely on a partially-trusted third party, the Custodian, that breaks the association between operator identities known to the licensing authority and identifiers used in broadcasts. At the same time, CAPSID allows a law enforcement authority to unseal anonymous identifiers with the aid of the Custodian. The Custodian protects operator privacy interests by ensuring that all legal requirements for unsealing have been met.

CAPSID may be viewed as an implementation of the session ID mechanism proposed by the FAA for its Remote ID system. The FAA's session ID mechanism does not provide broadcast authentication or protection against government tracking by the FAA itself. CAPSID remedies these shortcomings while meeting the stated goals of the FAA Remote ID system.

REFERENCES

- [1] 2011. Security analysis of the ADS-B implementation in the next generation air transportation system. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection* 4, 2 (2011), 78–87.
- [2] Amirhossein Asari, Mahdi R. Alagheband, Majid Bayat, and Maryam Rajabzadeh Asaar. 2021. A new provable hierarchical anonymous certificateless authentication protocol with aggregate verification in ADS-B systems. *Computer Networks* 185 (2021).
- [3] ASTM F3411 2022. *Standard Specification for Remote ID and Tracking*. Technical Report. ASTM International.
- [4] Maria Azees, Pandi Vijayakumar, and Lazarus Jegatha Deboarh. 2017. EAAP: Efficient Anonymous Authentication With Conditional Privacy-Preserving Scheme for Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* 18, 9 (2017), 2467–2476.
- [5] Mihir Bellare, Anand Desai, Eron Jookipii, and Phillip Rogaway. 1997. A concrete security treatment of symmetric encryption. In *Proceedings 38th Annual Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science*. IEEE, 394–403.
- [6] Mihir Bellare, Haixia Shi, and Chong Zhang. 2005. Foundations of group signatures: The case of dynamic groups. In *Cryptographers' track at the RSA conference*. Springer, 136–153.
- [7] Norbert Bißmeyer, Jonathan Petit, and Kpatcha M Bayarou. 2013. CoPRA: Conditional Pseudonym Resolution Algorithm in VANETs. In *Conference on Wireless On-demand Network Systems and Services (WONS)*. 9–16.
- [8] Bruno Blanchet. 2016. Modeling and Verifying Security Protocols with the Applied Pi Calculus and ProVerif. *Foundations and Trends® in Privacy and Security* 1, 1-2 (2016), 1–135.
- [9] Bruno Blanchet, Ben Smyth, Vincent Cheval, and Marc Sylvestre. 2023. ProVerif 2.05: Automatic Cryptographic Protocol Verifier, User Manual and Tutorial. <https://bblanche.gitlabpages.inria.fr/proverif/manual.pdf>.
- [10] Dan Boneh, Xavier Boyen, and Hovav Shacham. 2004. Short group signatures. In *Annual international cryptology conference*. Springer, 41–55.
- [11] Jonathan Bootle, Andrea Cerulli, Pyrros Chaidos, Essam Ghadafi, and Jens Groth. 2016. Foundations of Fully Dynamic Group Signatures. In *Applied Cryptography and Network Security*, Mark Manulis, Ahmad-Reza Sadeghi, and Steve Schneider (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, 117–136.
- [12] Booz Allen Hamilton. 2018. The Patient Safety Reporting System – Frequently Asked Questions. https://psrs.arc.nasa.gov/faq.html#why_nasa_involved.

- [13] Booz Allen Hamilton. 2024. ASRS – Aviation Safety Reporting System – Immunity Policies. <https://asrs.arc.nasa.gov/overview/immunity.html>.
- [14] Emily Cook. 2015. ADS-B, Friend or Foe: ADS-B Message Authentication for NextGen Aircraft. In *IEEE Conference on High Performance Computing and Communications*. 1256–1261.
- [15] Council of the Inspectors General on Integrity and Efficiency. [n. d.]. About Oversight.gov | Oversight.gov. <https://www.oversight.gov/about>.
- [16] Jie Cui, Di Wu, Jing Zhang, Yan Xu, and Hong Zhong. 2019. An Efficient Authentication Scheme Based on Semi-Trusted Authority in VANETs. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 68, 3 (2019), 2972–2986.
- [17] European Union Aviation Safety Agency. 2024. Easy Access Rules for Unmanned Aircraft Systems. <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/document-library/easy-access-rules/online-publications/easy-access-rules-unmanned-aircraft-systems?page=16>.
- [18] Facebook [n. d.]. Transparency reports | Transparency Center. <https://transparency.meta.com/reports>.
- [19] Federal Aviation Administration. 2021. Remote Identification of Unmanned Aircraft. <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2021-01-15/pdf/2020-28948.pdf>.
- [20] Lars Fischer, Amer Aijaz, Claudia Eckert, and David Vogt. 2006. Secure Revocable Anonymous Authenticated Inter-Vehicle Communication (SRAAC). In *4th Conference on Embedded Security in Cars (ESCAR)*.
- [21] David Goldschlag, Michael Reed, and Paul Syverson. 1999. Onion routing. *Commun. ACM* 42, 2 (1999), 39–41.
- [22] Google [n. d.]. Google Transparency Report. <https://transparencyreport.google.com>.
- [23] Holybro. 2024. Technical Specification – Holybro Docs. <https://docs.holybro.com/autopilot/pixhawk-6x/technical-specification>.
- [24] Japan Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism: Civil Aviation Bureau. 2022. Requirements for remote ID devices and applications. <https://www.mlit.go.jp/koku/content/001582250.pdf>.
- [25] Yanji Jiang, Shaocheng Ge, and Xueli Shen. 2020. AAAS: An anonymous authentication scheme based on group signature in VANETs. *IEEE Access* 8 (2020), 98986–98998.
- [26] P. Leach, M. Mealling, and R. Salz. 2005. *A Universally Unique Identifier (UUID) URN Namespace*. RFC 4122. Internet Engineering Task Force. <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc4122>
- [27] Xiong Li, Tian Liu, Mohammad S Obaidat, Fan Wu, Pandi Vijayakumar, and Neeraj Kumar. 2020. A lightweight privacy-preserving authentication protocol for VANETs. *IEEE Systems Journal* 14, 3 (2020), 3547–3557.
- [28] Moses Liskov, Ronald L Rivest, and David Wagner. 2002. Tweakable Block Ciphers. In *Advances in Cryptology (CRYPTO 2002): 22nd Annual International Cryptology Conference Santa Barbara, California, USA, August 18–22, 2002*. Springer, 31–46.
- [29] Lukas Malina, Arnau Vives-Guasch, Jordi Castella-Roca, Alexandre Viejo, and Jan Hajny. 2015. Efficient group signatures for privacy-preserving vehicular networks. *Telecommunication Systems* 58 (2015), 293–311.
- [30] Microsoft [n. d.]. Digital Safety | Transparency reports. <https://www.microsoft.com/en/digitalsafety/transparency-reports>.
- [31] Mark L. Psiaki and Todd E. Humphreys. 2016. GNSS Spoofing and Detection. *Proc. IEEE* 104, 6 (2016), 1258–1270.
- [32] RaceDayQuads. 2021. FAA Legal Battle – Challenging Remote ID – RaceDayQuads. <https://www.racedayquads.com/pages/faa-legal-battle-to-save-fpv>.
- [33] Maxim Raya and Jean-Pierre Hubaux. 2007. Securing vehicular ad hoc networks. *Journal of computer security* 15, 1 (2007), 39–68.
- [34] Jonathan Rupprecht, Elizabeth Candelario, and Kathleen Yodice. 2021. On Petition for Review of a Final Rule Of the Federal Aviation Administration, Brief of Petitioners. United States Court of Appeals for the District of Columbia, No. 21-1087.
- [35] Florian Schaub, Frank Kargl, Zhendong Ma, and Michael Weber. 2010. V-Tokens for Conditional Pseudonymity in VANETs. In *2010 IEEE Wireless Communication and Networking Conference*. 1–6.
- [36] SEGGER. [n. d.]. emSecure-ECDsa: Digital Signatures. <https://www.segger.com/products/security-iot/emsecure/variations/emsecure-ecdsa>.
- [37] Jun Shao, Xiaodong Lin, Rongxing Lu, and Cong Zuo. 2016. A Threshold Anonymous Authentication Protocol for VANETs. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* 65, 3 (2016), 1711–1720.
- [38] Pietro Tedeschi, Savio Sciancalepore, and Roberto Di Pietro. 2021. ARID: Anonymous remote identification of unmanned aerial vehicles. In *Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*. 207–218.
- [39] Pietro Tedeschi, Savio Sciancalepore, and Roberto Di Pietro. 2021. ARID: Anonymous remote identification of unmanned aerial vehicles. In *Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*. 207–218.
- [40] Shibin Wang and Nianmin Yao. 2017. LLAP: A local identity-based anonymous message authentication protocol in VANETs. *Computer Communications* 112 (2017), 154–164.
- [41] Eva Wisse, Pietro Tedeschi, Savio Sciancalepore, and Roberto Di Pietro. 2023. A 2RID-Anonymous Direct Authentication and Remote Identification of Commercial Drones. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* (2023).
- [42] Eva Wisse, Pietro Tedeschi, Savio Sciancalepore, and Roberto Di Pietro. 2023. A²RID—Anonymous Direct Authentication and Remote Identification of Commercial Drones. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 10, 12 (2023), 10587–10604.
- [43] Dawn Zoldi. 2021. This Case Against The FAA Could Revector The Commercial Drone Industry. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/dawnzoldi/2021/10/05/this-case-against-the-faa-could-revector-the-commercial-drone-industry>.

A OPERATOR NON-LINKABILITY

In this section, we show that neither a corrupt Adversary nor a corrupt Custodian, on their own, can link an operator across operational epochs. (The miscreant operator has a subset of their capabilities.) We prove non-linkability in the standard model of cryptography. To our knowledge, this kind of reasoning is not yet possible in ProVerif, so we provide a written proof.

Formally, we show that the E-certs and F-certs are not linkable between epochs. Since both are constructed in essentially the same way (compare Eq. 3 and 6), we prove the non-linkability of the common construction, which depends on security of the tweakable block cipher used to produce the EOIDs, EUIDs, FOIDs, and FUIDs. The core of the proof is a *non-linkability experiment*, described next.

A.1 Non-Linkability Experiment

In the non-linkability experiment, an adversary is challenged to distinguish between two sets of *proto-certificates* constructed analogously to E-certs and F-certs, but containing only the (EOID,EUID) or (FOID,FUID) elements.

Let \tilde{E} be the encryption function of a tweakable block cipher:

$$\tilde{E} : \{0, 1\}^k \times \{0, 1\}^\ell \times \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^n.$$

(We do not use decryption in the non-linkability experiment.) Choose n large enough so that $\{0, 1\}^n$ can encode all OIDs and UIDs (e.g., $n = 128$ for a tweakable block cipher based on AES), and let $\ell = 1 + n$. We assume that epochs are encoded as an n bit binary value. Now fix some k and n . Then define:

$$\text{PCERT}_\kappa(i, o, u) = (\tilde{E}_\kappa(0||i, o), \tilde{E}_\kappa(1||\tilde{E}_\kappa(0||i, o), u)) \quad (8)$$

Note that this is the same construction as Eqs. 3 and 6, but without the public key and authority signature.

The use of a tweakable block cipher serves two purposes. First, it allows the Authority and Custodian to each use a single encryption key. This greatly simplifies the reduction below, by allowing us to turn a non-linkability adversary into a chosen plaintext attack adversary against the block cipher. An alternative construction, which we also believe to be secure, would be to use a key derivation function to generate separate symmetric keys for each epoch, however this does not completely eliminate the need for tweaking. The second reason for using a tweaked block cipher is to make the EUID depend on the OID (and the FUID depend on the EOID). This ensures that the same UAV identifier (UID) registered by two different operators will result in different EUIDs and FUIDs, preventing an attacker from using information from one operator’s registration to de-anonymize another.

Define a left-or-right function in the usual way: $\text{LR}(x, y, 0) = x$ and $\text{LR}(x, y, 1) = y$. The adversary is given left-or-right access to a PCERT oracle:

$$\mathcal{O}_{\kappa,b}(i, o_0, u_0, o_1, u_1) = \text{PCERT}_\kappa(i, \text{LR}(o_0, o_1, b), \text{LR}(u_0, u_1, b))$$

The adversary tries to guess b based on the output of the oracle. However, in our experiment, for each epoch i and OID o , the adversary is allowed to query the oracle at most once when $o = o_0 \neq o_1$, or $o_0 \neq o_1 = o$, or $o = o_0 = o_1$ but $u_0 \neq u_1$. Or the adversary is allowed to query any number of times, if for every query $o_0 = o_1$ and $u_0 = u_1$. We call the former a *challenge query* and the latter a *regular query*. A challenge query gives the adversary one of two possible P-certs, depending on $b \in \{0, 1\}$, while a regular query is simply direct access to the P-cert function (without revealing κ).

Note that the adversary can win trivially by issuing a challenge query and then two regular queries for the left and right values separately. To prevent this, we require that for a given epoch i , the adversary may either query an OID exactly once in a challenge query, or any number of times in a regular query.

In CAPSID terms, this is equivalent to a corrupt Authority adversary knowing the F-cert of a given operator for some set of epochs and then trying to infer, for some other epoch, whether a given F-cert belongs to the same operator. We make the job as easy as possible for the adversary by asking it to distinguish between one of two possible F-certs whose EOIDS are chosen by the adversary.

Similarly, the experiment models a corrupt Custodian knowing the E-cert of a given operator for some set of epochs and then trying to infer, for some other epoch, whether a given E-cert belongs to the same operator. In this case, the corrupt Custodian adversary is allowed to create as many E-certs as it wants using any OIDs and UIDs it wants.

If the adversary issues queries that satisfy the query restrictions, we call the experiment *fair*. We modify the oracle $O_{\kappa,b}$ to keep track of the queries issued by the adversary and whether the experiment is fair using a global variable *fair*:

```

Oracle  $O_{\kappa,b}(i, o_0, u_0, o_1, u_1)$  is
  if  $o_0 \neq o_1$  or  $u_0 \neq u_1$  then
    if  $(i, o_0) \in Q_R \cup Q_C$  or  $(i, o_1) \in Q_R \cup Q_C$  then
       $fair \leftarrow FALSE$ 
    end
     $Q_C \leftarrow Q_C \cup \{(i, o_0), (i, o_1)\}$ 
  else
    if  $(i, o_0) \in Q_C$  then
       $fair \leftarrow FALSE$ 
    end
     $Q_R \leftarrow Q_R \cup \{(i, o_0)\}$ 
  end
  return  $PCERT_{\kappa}(i, LR(o_0, o_1, b), LR(u_0, u_1, b))$ 

```

The sets Q_R and Q_C are used to keep track of the epoch and OID combinations of regular and challenge queries, respectively. The *then* branch of the outer *if* statement corresponds to challenge queries, the *else* branch to regular queries.

Now let A be an adversary that has access to oracle O . We define the non-linkability experiment as:

Experiment $\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk-}b}(A)$ is

```

 $fair \leftarrow TRUE$ 
 $Q_R \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
 $Q_C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
 $\kappa \xleftarrow{R} \{0, 1\}^k$ 
 $c \leftarrow A^{O_{\kappa,b}(\cdot)}$ 
if  $fair$  then
  return  $c$ 
else
  return  $1 - b$ 

```

The experiment penalizes an adversary that breaks the fair experiment rules. We define the *advantage of the adversary* A as:

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(A) = \Pr[\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk-}1}(A) = 1] - \Pr[\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk-}0}(A) = 1].$$

We define the *advantage of the P-cert scheme* as:

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(k, n, t, q) = \max_A \{\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E},A}^{\text{nlk}}\},$$

where the maximum is taken over all adversaries A making at most q queries and running in at most t time, for fixed keys size k and block size n .

The non-linkability experiment models a corrupt Authority that learns learn, through some other channels, real users' FOIDS and FUIDs for some subset of epochs. We ask corrupt Authority to distinguish the F-certs of real operators of its own choosing in an epoch of its own choosing for which it does not already know their F-certs. We further advantage the adversary by allowing multiple correlated challenges and by allowing the adversary to choose arbitrary epoch values i . Assuming that an operator does not fly her UAV during an epoch for which the corrupt Authority has learned her FOID, the threat model maps to the proto-certificate game described above.

Similarly, the experiment also models a corrupt Custodian that learns the mapping between OIDs and EOIDS (or UIDs and EUIDs) for some epochs. We give the corrupt Custodian the further benefit of allowing it to choose the OIDs and UIDs of the real operators, as in the proto-certificate experiment described above.

A.2 The Tweakable Block Cipher Experiment

We apply the formalism of Bellare *et al.* [5] to tweakable block ciphers [28] to define a *twk-prp-cpa* experiment, intended to capture the security of a tweakable block cipher. We use k to denote the key size, ℓ the tweak size, and n the block size of the tweakable block cipher. Let A be an adversary that has access to an oracle,

$$O_{\kappa,b}^{\text{twk-prp}}(w, m) \equiv \text{LR}(\tilde{\Pi}(w, m), \tilde{E}_{\kappa}(w, m), b),$$

where $w \in \{0, 1\}^{\ell}$ is the tweak and $m \in \{0, 1\}^n$ is the plaintext. As in the original definition [28], $\tilde{\Pi}$ is a family of independent random permutations parameterized by the first argument.

Define the twk-prp-cpa experiment as:

Experiment $\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-}b}(A)$ is
 $\kappa \xleftarrow{R} \{0, 1\}^k$
 return $A^{O_{\kappa,b}^{\text{twk-prp}}}$

Define the advantage of the above adversary as:

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(A) = \Pr [\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-1}}(A) = 1] \quad (9)$$

$$- \Pr [\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-0}}(A) = 1].$$

and

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(k, \ell, n, t, q) = \max_A \{\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(A)\},$$

where the maximum is taken over all adversaries making q queries to the oracle and running in t time for fixed key size k , tweak size ℓ , and block size n .

A.3 Reduction Algorithm Construction

Let A_{nlk} represent any potential adversary in the non-linkability experiment. Our goal is to demonstrate an adversary $A_{\text{twk-prp}}$ for the twk-prp-cpa experiment. Our adversary will use A_{nlk} internally to attack the tweaked block cipher \tilde{E} . Let $O^{\text{twk-prp}}$ be the oracle provided to $A_{\text{twk-prp}}$, and let O_b^{nlk} denote the oracle we must provide to A_{nlk} . Following Bellare *et al.* [5], our adversary simulates the non-linkability experiment. If the non-linkability adversary wins, we declare that we were interacting with the tweaked block cipher. Otherwise, we declare that we were interacting with a random oracle:

Algorithm $A_{\text{twk-prp}}^{O^{\text{twk-prp}}}$ is:
 $b \xleftarrow{R} \{0, 1\}$
 $d \leftarrow A_{\text{nlk}}^{O_b^{\text{nlk}}}()$
 if $b = d$ then
 return 1
 else
 return 0

We also need to provide the non-linkability adversary with a non-linkability oracle. Our P-cert oracle O_b^{nlk} calls the $O_{\kappa,b}^{\text{twk-prp}}$ oracle to realize the tweaked block cipher in Eq. 8.

A.4 Adversary Advantage Relationship

We are now ready to prove the relationship between two adversaries' advantages:

PROPOSITION 1. *For any tweakable block cipher \tilde{E} with key size k , block size n and tweak size $n + 1$,*

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(k, n, t, q) \leq$$

$$2 \cdot \text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(k, n + 1, n, t + O(q(n + k)), 2q) + \frac{q^2}{2^{n-2}}.$$

PROOF. First, note that when considering the advantage of a P-cert scheme (Eq. A.1), we only need to consider fair adversaries. (A fair adversary is one that only makes fair queries.) This is because the non-linkability experiment penalizes unfair adversaries. For any adversary that makes an unfair query, there is an adversary

that behaves the same way up to the point of issuing an unfair query; then, instead of issuing the unfair query, stops and returns the result of a fair coin flip. Such an adversary has an advantage that is at least as high as the unfair adversary it is mimicking.

We will show that for any fair adversary A_{nlk} , our adversary $A_{\text{twk-prp}}$, which will use A_{nlk} , achieves:

$$\text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(A_{\text{twk-prp}}) > \frac{1}{2} \text{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(A_{\text{nlk}}) - \frac{q^2}{2^{n-1}}.$$

We begin by showing that,

$$\Pr [\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-0}}(A_{\text{twk-prp}}) = 1] < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{q^2}{2^{n-1}}.$$

This is the scenario where the non-linkability adversary inside our adversary gets access to a P-cert oracle instantiated with a tweaked random permutation $\tilde{\Pi}$. We will show that in this case, the output of left-or-right P-cert oracle O_b^{nlk} we provide to A_{nlk} is identically distributed when $b = 0$ and when $b = 1$.

The left-or-right P-cert oracle takes a 5-tuple consisting of the epoch i , OIDs o_0 and o_1 , and UIDs u_0 and u_1 . Let $\tilde{\Pi}_X(w, m)$ denote $\tilde{\Pi}(0 \| w, m)$ and $\tilde{\Pi}_Y(w, m)$ denote $\tilde{\Pi}(1 \| w, m)$. Let $X_b = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i, o_b)$ and $Y_b = \tilde{\Pi}_Y(X_b, u_b)$, so that the output of the left-or-right P-cert oracle is (X_b, Y_b) .

Note that for any i , the permutations $\tilde{\Pi}_X(i, \cdot)$ and $\tilde{\Pi}_Y(X_b, \cdot)$ are independent because the tweak spaces are disjoint. Therefore, X_b and Y_b are independent random variables.

Now consider the distributions of X_0 and X_1 . Each epoch corresponds to a distinct tweak, so for any two epochs $i \neq i'$, the permutations $\tilde{\Pi}_X(i, \cdot)$ and $\tilde{\Pi}_X(i', \cdot)$ are independent. Now consider some specific epoch i .

A fair adversary can submit a challenge query with a given OID o at most once, and that value o cannot be queried again in that epoch, in either a challenge or a regular query. Since neither o_0 nor o_1 have been queried, the random variables $X_0 = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i, o_0)$ and $X_1 = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i, o_1)$ are identically distributed conditioned on the result of past queries.

Now consider the distribution of Y_0 and Y_1 . If the values X_0 and X_1 have never appeared query, then $Y_0 = \tilde{\Pi}_Y(X_0, u_0)$ and $Y_1 = \tilde{\Pi}_Y(X_1, u_1)$ are identically distributed conditioned on the result of past queries. This is true for the current epoch i , since o_0 and o_1 have not been queried in the current epoch. However, it is possible that the adversary has found another epoch i' and OID o' such that $X_0 = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i, o_0) = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i', o')$ or $X_1 = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i, o_1) = \tilde{\Pi}_X(i', o')$. The probability of such a collision after q queries is no more than $2q(2q - 1)/2^{n+1} < q^2/2^{n-1}$, since each query reveals at most two OID values. Thus,

$$\Pr [\text{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-0}}(A_{\text{twk-prp}}) = 1] < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{q^2}{2^{n-1}}$$

Now consider the twk-prp-cpa-1 experiment, when the encryption oracle is instantiated with the tweaked block cipher. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Pr [\mathbf{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa-1}}(A_{\text{twk-prp}}) = 1] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \Pr [A_{\text{nlk}}^{O_0^{\text{nlk}}} \text{ outputs } 0] + \frac{1}{2} \Pr [A_{\text{nlk}}^{O_1^{\text{nlk}}} \text{ outputs } 1] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \Pr [\mathbf{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk-0}}(A_{\text{nlk}}) = 1] \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \Pr [\mathbf{Exp}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk-1}}(A_{\text{nlk}}) = 1] \\
&= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(A_{\text{nlk}}).
\end{aligned}$$

Using Eq. 9 to combine the results above:

$$\mathbf{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{twk-prp-cpa}}(A_{\text{twk-prp}}) > \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{Adv}_{\tilde{E}}^{\text{nlk}}(A_{\text{nlk}}) - \frac{q^2}{2^{n-1}}.$$

Our adversary $A_{\text{twk-prp}}$ makes two queries to the tweaked block cipher oracle for each query to the P-cert oracle made by the non-linkability adversary. Its running time is that of the adversary plus $O(n+k)$ overhead per query. \square